

ESiWACE3 Success Story:

Accelerating the Dutch atmospheric large-eddy simulation achieving a 12x speedup for a high-resolution local weather model with modern graphics cards

Challenge

- High-fidelity weather and climate simulations are computationally expensive due to their multiscale and multi-physics nature, requiring atmospheric large-eddy simulations (LES) on grids with billions of cells using many processors.
- Models like the Dutch Atmospheric Large-Eddy Simulation (DALES) have long development cycles and rely on a large Fortran90 code base, which is not easily rewritten in modern, GPU-friendly languages.
- Additionally, DALES is used by researchers and students, for whom the Fortran90 syntax is more accessible compared to advanced computing-focused languages.

Solution

- Using OpenACC to accelerate the various physics modules and atmospheric dynamics with minimum disruption of the code base. OpenACC is well suited for this task as it seamlessly integrates in the Fortran90 DALES code. eScience Center RSEs have expanded the work to include all of DALES core modules in two steps:
 - 1) implementing OpenACC directives and replacing the radiation scheme with the GPU-aware RTE-RRTMGP library,
 - 2) iteratively profile and optimize the code obtained after the first step to ensure good performances on the GPU, while maintaining the baseline CPU performances and code readability.

Benefits

20x

20x speedup for a single Nvidia A100 GPU compared to a single (AMD EPYC) CPU

Substantial energy savings for longer runs

12x

On a node-by-node basis for large test cases, a 12x speedup

Societal & economic impact

The hyper-resolution LES can significantly improve predictions of summer heavy rain and extreme temperatures in urban areas, which are expected to worsen in the coming decades.

At cloud-resolving resolutions, it can enhance the accuracy of predicting the yield of photovoltaics and wind turbines, aiding in balancing power supply and demand in a renewable energy system.

Additionally, GPU acceleration allows DALES to be used for local climate projections, providing detailed and reliable climate information to stakeholders in agriculture, infrastructure, and other sectors.

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More info: www.esiwace.eu/services

